

Digital Innovation of Banyuwangi Government in Encouraging Improvement of Public Services and Social Development

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ABSTRACT: *Developing countries are starting to compete to improve their social welfare through innovation. Meanwhile, at the regional level, Policy Reform is also implemented in Indonesia to build a digital society and public services. This study aims to analyze innovation policies that can adapt to changes in public services and development and analyze the construction of organizational culture in Banyuwangi Regency in supporting changes in public services and development. The approach used in this research is qualitative. Data processing results are interpreted using the type of social policy research. The research location is in the regional command of Banyuwangi Regency, East Java Province, Republic of Indonesia. This study showed that the regional government issued a public service policy by developing a digital ecosystem called Smart Kampung. Smart Kampung is an integrated village development program that combines fiber optic-based ICT, productive economic activities, creative economic activities, health-education improvement, and poverty alleviation efforts. The parties involved in developing the smart kampung program, namely the government, support this program; the leadership factor and the provision of regulations are the main keys in implementing the program, as well as the involvement of the private sector and the community in social development.*

KEYWORDS -Local Government, Public Policy, Public Service, Digital Innovation, Social Development

I. INTRODUCTION

Social development in Indonesia itself is inseparable from local governments' efforts in carrying out their social transformation. Digital innovation has been present in local government in the last few decades. The government has intensified Dilan's "Digital Melayani" principle in providing public services (Budianta, 2020). This is important because digital services are a demand that will be able to get closer to the community. Developing countries are starting to compete to improve their social welfare through innovation (Mwita, 2002; Razavi&Attarnezhad, 2013). The opinion of world leaders began to change along with the opening of their views on issues of humanity. At the global level, international organizations through the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) organize forums from several countries worldwide on governance and innovation.

Meanwhile, the Review of Regulatory is also carried out at the local level in Indonesia. This is actually in line with the spirit of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (Amendment IV) in article 31, paragraph 5, which states that "The government advances science and technology by upholding religious values and national unity for the advancement of civilization and the welfare of mankind. " The involvement of the state in the welfare of its citizens cannot be separated from the state's role in development, especially social development, and therefore social welfare development is closely related to the three grand ideologies related to

how big the role of the state in economic and social development which then gave birth to the welfare state system, namely: understanding liberalism, conservatism, and structuralism (Suharto, 2006b; see Parsons et al. 1994; DuBois dan Miley, 2005).

One of the three views, namely liberalism, argues that the state has the legitimacy to regulate and act in the development process. Three state interventions needed in development include (a) the creation of income distribution, (b) stabilization of the private market mechanism, and (c) the provision of public goods that are incapable or inefficient if provided by the market. The importance of the state's role in achieving social development goals in practice is also still seen as a strategy for achieving several existing strategies, including approaches that rely on the active role of government through social services or social policy approaches, or social administration approaches (Midgley, 1995) or through a development approach, which supports social welfare programs, the active role of the government and the involvement of professionals in social planning (Zastrow, 2000).

In addition to facilitating and directing social development so that it follows the objectives to be achieved, the state should also contribute directly to social development through various policies and strategic public sectors that directly regulate the management and distribution of public resources (natural, financial, and human) for the benefit of the people at large widely and sustainably as well as ensuring that the policies and regulations he makes can influence the process of changing society to accelerate the realization of the achievement of community welfare through improving public services, empowering and involving community participation in the development process (Zastrow 2000, Midgley 2005 in Suharto 2009, Adi 2008).

In the context of innovation, the Government of Indonesia has issued Law Number 11 of 2019 concerning the National System for Research, Development, and Application of Science and Technology which mandates the Government and Regional Governments to strengthen the carrying capacity of science and technology in increasing the nation's competitiveness and independence in facing global competition. Then the regulation of innovation in regional government is mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government by issuing derivative regulations in the form of Government Regulation Number 38 of 2017 concerning Regional Innovation. This regulation explains that regional innovation is all forms of reform in regional government administration.

In line with the above objectives, decentralization or regional autonomy has provided opportunities for local governments with their authority to try to strengthen public services in favor of the public interest. These innovations emerged with the presence of fiber optic devices and a set of internet. With this infrastructure, the local government and the community can exchange information and create a network society. In this study, the focus is on the purpose of answering the formulation of the problem. How are the efforts of the Banyuwangi district government in implementing a dynamic government model in changing public services and development in Banyuwangi Regency?

According to Castells (Fitzpatrick, 2005), The network society is the Information Age in which society regulates the production and distribution of information and has replaced the paradigm of the Industrial Age, which was organized primarily around energy production and distribution. Castells describes a network society in terms of six main features, which he relates to recent social transformations around the world, namely informational, network society, the global economy or informational economy, the transformation of the workforce, global city, and cyberculture.

The explanation of the network community is indeed inseparable from the existence of digital innovation. Digital innovation is built on using digital technology during the innovation process or results (Nambisan et al., 2017). Opportunities to innovate by digitizing products and offering digital services prove to challenge for an organization (e.g., Henfridsson et al., 2014; Svahn, Mathiassen, & Lindgren, 2017). In contrast to the traditional value chain structure, which usually exists in traditional industries, value in digital innovation is created through distributed control and dynamic processes in a networked environment (Boland Jr, Lyytinen, & Yoo, 2007; Westergren & Holmström, 2012). At the core of digital innovation, we find digitization, which refers to the encoding of analog information into a digital format (Tilson, Lyytinen, & Sorensen, 2010; Yoo et al., 2012).

However, the massive creation of digital innovations in society should be balanced by local governments throughout Indonesia. For example, some of the obstacles in local government come from planning and budgeting. Rudiantara explained, If 80% of the total regional budget is allocated for routine local government spending, it will be difficult to develop a smart city. The reason is that only 20% of the total regional budget remains that can be used for shopping for goods to support smart cities (Rosandya, 2017). In fact, if you look at the use of the internet in the archipelago, Indonesia is now transforming into a digitally oriented society. At least this can be seen from three indicators: (1) the highest internet penetration rate in Asia, (2) the penetration of cellular cards that exceed the population, and (3) the use of social networks, which is very dominant in Indonesia.

Regarding the determination of how the government seeks the welfare of the people and the achievement of the long-term goals of a nation, in a democratic country, the way to be taken is to involve all stakeholders, namely the government, the private sector, and the community in formulating policies, establishing institutions and patterns of relationships between stakeholders. Related to this understanding, Boon, and Geraldine (2007: 52) define governance as “the chosen path, policies, institutions and the resultant structures that collectively provide the incentives and constraints to facilitate or impede interactions that lead to economic progress and social wellbeing” (the determination of various policies, institutions and structures selected, which together encourage to facilitate interaction towards economic progress and a better social life).

This research was conducted in Banyuwangi Regency by digging deeper into digital innovation policies in an area with the challenges of strong traditional community characteristics. Interesting to be the locus of study, the Banyuwangi Regency Government has many public services, regional development, and innovation awards.

Several experts recently also done new research around social innovation (Bria, 2015). This research looks at the possibility of a future where services are explicitly designed to address societal challenges such as climate change and unemployment. This research project has identified, mapped, and engaged communities building on the emerging field of Digital Social Innovation and provided policy recommendations to encourage, support, and scale up Digital Social Innovation in Europe. In addition, this research illustrates that a new set of online services is being developed as there is renewed interest from citizens across Europe in solving social and economic challenges.

Other Innovation Research emerged from (Maiolini, Marra, Baldassarri, & Carlei, 2016). The purpose of the article is twofold. First, this article offers an empirical acknowledgment to the audience that innovation is in the field of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by investigating large-scale, social, and innovative activities carried out by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) around the world in 2001 and 2014. Second, the article intends to capture the core business of social innovation and the underlying complementarity between products, markets, and technology and show where digital media and Information Technology are essentially tracking the trajectory of innovation across many industries, leading the current pattern of the social innovation industry.

As for research in Indonesia, an example (Utami, 2014) examines Taman Cerdas with the development of Taman Cerdas in Surakarta City. (Purnomowati&Ismi, 2014) conducted research in the city of Malang. This study measures smart cities from six aspects: smart economy, smart society, smart mobility, smart environment, smart living, and smart government. Meanwhile (Pongsapan, Rindengan, & Najoan, 2014) describes their studies in the architectural design of communication and information networks. The study explained that at that time, the City of Manado still did not have an information and communication telecommunications network that connected all existing agencies within the scope of the Manado City Government, so a model was made for eight areas of information and communication technology networks that were expected to support Manado as a Smart City. The importance of digital social innovation is increasing along with the high dynamics of change in modern society in recent times and with the growth of structural and cultural differentiation, which diversifies, differentiates, individualizes, and negates the human social world.

However, the research above emphasizes certain elements, namely the creation of product innovation. In contrast to the research conducted above, this study seeks to examine local governments' efforts in public services and development by applying digital innovation and network society as the application of dynamic

governance. Some of the discussions in this study are how the various policies, institutions, and structures that have been selected work so that they can adapt to the uncertainty and rapid change in the environment so that these policies, institutions, and structures remain relevant and effective in achieving long-term desires for the community.

II. METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach. Qualitative research uses a natural setting to interpret the phenomena that occur. The research aims to answer a general question that can be answered after answering three specific questions. Research questions are open-ended questions that require in-depth understanding, which can be done through observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation studies (Strauss & Corbin, 1994). The informant collection technique was used with a purposive sampling technique (Bryman, 2012). In analyzing the data, the researcher uses coding as the analysis process (Rubin, Allen; Babbie, 2011). According to (Strauss & Corbin, 1994b) Strauss and Corbin, there are three types of data analysis processes, namely open coding, axial coding, and selective coding. First, open coding is the process of detailing, testing, comparing, conceptualizing, and categorizing data. Second, axial coding is a set of procedures in which data are reassembled in a new way after open coding by making connections between categories. This is done by utilizing the coding paradigm, which includes conditions, contexts, action, interaction strategies, and consequences, and the third is selective coding, in which the core category selection process systematically links to other categories, performs validates those relationships, and puts them into categories that are needed further for improvement and development.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Village Development Policies and 'Smart Kampung' Regulations

The Banyuwangi Regency government initiated the Smart Kampung concept. The Regent's regulation Number 18 of 2016 concerning the Integration of Village/Urban Village-Based Work Programs through Smart Kampung defines Smart Kampung as a concept of community development in a community to do things intelligently, smartly, and wisely in overcoming various problems. Smart kampung is also regulated in Banyuwangi Regent Regulation Number 16 of 2017 concerning implementing Smart City Masterplans through Banyuwangi smart villages.

Based on the Banyuwangi Regent Regulation Number 16 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of the Smart City Masterplan through the Banyuwangi smart village, the intended target of organizing a smart kampung is:

- a. Realizing effective, efficient, communicative local government governance and governance and continuously improving bureaucratic performance through innovation and integrated technology adoption
- b. Increase competitiveness by developing three elements, namely tourism, business and the face of the city
- c. Creating an ecosystem that supports community economic activities that are in line with the leading regional economic sectors that are adaptive to changes that occur in the current information age, as well as increasing public financial literacy through various programs including realizing a less-cash society.
- d. Ensuring the feasibility of the community's standard of living through the feasibility of a lifestyle, the quality of health, and the feasibility of transportation modes to support the mobility of people and goods
- e. Realizing a socio-technical ecosystem of a humanist and dynamic society, both physical and virtual for the creation of a productive, communicative and interactive society, with high digital literacy
- f. Managing a smart environment and realizing sustainable development.

Smart Kampung is digital innovation in the Banyuwangi area stipulated through Regent Regulation 60 of 2017 concerning implementing the Smart City Masterplan through the Banyuwangi Smart Kampung. Smart Kampung is the name of the application used to provide digital public service innovation services. According to

the informant, the term smart village refers to a village that is smart in providing public services and an independent village in terms of funding. The "Smart Kampung" program designs villages to have an integrated program framework that combines fiber-optic-based ICT, productive economic activities, creative economic activities, health-education improvement, and poverty alleviation efforts. The informant explained that at first, Smart Kampung was only used for services, but over time, Smart Kampung was used for other things.

One of these programs is to bring public services closer to the village level. To support the smooth running of Smart Kampung, each village is equipped with an operator who the local government has intensively trained. They are given training on the internet knowledge, the operation of ICT-based public services, to the use of internet marketing. This operator will be a bridge for residents to optimize the use of ICT in the village. The informant explained that each Bumdes employs IT staff who are paid from the Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) results. IT staff work and get a salary from Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes).

3.2 Analysis of the Application of Digitak Innovation in Public Services

All digital innovations in Banyuwangi Regency start from smart kampung innovations. The Banyuwangi Regency government initiated the Smart Kampung concept. The Regent's regulation Number 18 of 2016 concerning the Integration of Village/Urban Village-Based Work Programs through Smart Kampung defines Smart Kampung as a concept of community development in a community to do things intelligently, smartly, and wisely in overcoming various problems. Smart kampung is also regulated in Banyuwangi Regent Regulation Number 16 of 2017 concerning implementing Smart City Masterplan through Banyuwangi smart kampung. From this smart kampung, various digital innovations emerged that were used to facilitate services to the community. Various public service activities are carried out online so that various facilities can be obtained easily by the people of Banyuwangi in particular.

This change in public services cannot be separated from government support. Although change depends on local governments to innovate, implementing innovation requires support from the central government. Government support in implementing innovation, namely: first, providing an example that becomes a signal for local governments about the seriousness of innovating. While the second is that the support from the central and local governments needs to facilitate the formation of various mechanisms to support innovation through capacity building and encourage budget certainty. This includes building institutions by facilitating learning, encouraging local initiatives, funding innovative projects, or providing special funds to help regions make changes. Taufik (2005) states that the progress of innovation in the regions is actually not only driven by an increase in R&D, the diffusion of its results, or the innovation activities of the private sector, but also innovation or improvement in the government environment and improvement of its policies. Meanwhile, Jamrozik & Nocella (1998) explain that changes in public services cannot be separated from the underlying social and political policies. According to Jamrozik, social policy is a series of processes that include three levels, namely the political sphere, the administrative sphere, and the operational sphere. The political level is the policy planning and formulation. The administrative level is the process of interpreting and formulating policies into a series of more operational activities. The interpretation process serves as a framework for the operational level where the actual social services are carried out directly to the community (service-receiving public).

Innovation and policy are two terms that complement each other. Innovation is present as a new product and its nature replaces the old way. Likewise, the nature of the policies that exist to replace foreign policies that are not in accordance with the times. The government has 3 (three) roles in innovating policies, namely (Mulgan et al., 2007):

- 1. Policy innovation, new policy direction and initiatives.** The policy innovation in question is the existence of new policy initiatives and directions. Every (public) policy issued in principle must contain something new. In particular, policy innovation according to Walker "policy innovation is a policy which is new to the states adopting it, no matter how old the program may be or how many other states may have adopted it"(Tyran & Sausgruber, 2003). So what is meant by policy innovation according to Walker is a policy that is new to the country that adopts it, regardless of how outdated the program is or how many other countries have adopted it before.

2. **Innovations in the policy-making process (innovation in the policy-making process).** In this role, the focus is on innovations that affect the process of making or formulating policies. For example, the process of policy formulation so far has not facilitated the participation of community members or related stakeholders. Whereas Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System requires citizen participation. Therefore, the innovation that emerges is how to integrate citizen participation mechanisms in the policy formulation process.
3. **Policy to foster innovation and its diffusion.** The policy in question is a policy specifically created to encourage and develop, as well as spread innovation in various sectors. In this regard (Frances Stokes William, 2018) explains that the spread of policy innovation occurs by referring to two important determinants, namely internal determinants and regional diffusion. Internal determinants or internal determinants are the social, economic, and political characteristics of a country that determine the innovativeness of a country. While regional diffusion or regional diffusion is the possibility of a country adopting a certain policy is higher if its neighboring countries have adopted the policy.

An illustrative example of the internal determinants that cause policy innovation is socio-economic changes in an area, public demonstrations, and political instability that forces fundamental policy changes related to the public interest. Regional diffusion occurs when a neighboring area or another area applies certain policies we imitate.

In the context of smart kampung programs and activities in Banyuwangi Regency, policies are carried out at the village level, and the village government and the community have a large enough share to campaign for the success of this digital Innovation during lay society. For example, Innovation is aspired to be an easy thing to follow for some people but a very difficult thing for others. For this reason, socialization and training for the community are important things, and this is where the role of the village government is to continue to socialize various regional innovations carried out to the community so that the goals that have been set can be achieved. The informant said that the use of technology would have a good impact on the performance of the village government so that performance becomes faster and more efficient.

Figure 1. Smart Kampung Public Service Change Model

Digital innovations carried out by the Banyuwangi government will indirectly affect the social pattern of the community. The public will find it easier to accept digitalization nationally because they use regional digital innovations. This digital innovation will help the community easily adapt to increasingly sophisticated technological developments. The informant said that digital innovation, especially in the economy, would

increase the circulation of existing money and directly increase people's purchasing power. This increased public purchasing power will ultimately increase local tax revenues.

This early concept of digital governance became popular when new public management thinking (NPM) was influencing governments worldwide (Lips, 2020). This has resulted in many countries seeing alignment regarding the strategic use of e-government to achieve NPM goals by increasing customer orientation in government and providing more efficient and effective public services (Homburg, 2004, 2008).

The application of e-Government aims to improve the effectiveness of government processes and services provided to the community (Hernikawati, 2013). Historically, in 1999, the implementation of E-government carried out at the US National Science Foundation adopted the term "digital government" as a new concept that covers aspects of e-government and e-democracy, including the use of digital technology to provide public services, support public policies, improving government operations, and involving citizens (Dawes, 2008). At that time, e-government was seen as a narrower perspective that could be associated with the public who supported the Internet as a service provider for scholars and practitioners, seeing additional opportunities to study or experiment with various new democratic innovation.

3.3 Community Network and Social Development

To overcome the problem of social inequality, the Banyuwangi Regency Government also pays attention to family resilience. In terms of increasing family resilience, each individual can be empowered to become a supporter of the fulfillment of basic family needs. However, social inequality also occurs due to poverty, where the poverty rate in Banyuwangi Regency in 2020 is still recorded at 8.06% and is concentrated in rural areas. For this reason, equitable development needs to be implemented using a development approach that starts from the village to minimize the social gap between the village and the city. In addition, rural communities, especially those included in the labor force, have an important role in alleviating poverty in Banyuwangi Regency, so it needs to be developed, both in the context of providing employment information and developing human resource competencies, job protection to providing business assistance.

On the other hand, the provision of social assistance to the poor is ensured to be right on target and effective so that the implementation of poverty alleviation in Banyuwangi Regency can run effectively. The social problem in Banyuwangi Regency that still needs serious attention is poverty because of the high number of poor families and the unmet needs of the poor and vulnerable communities through targeted social assistance. It is recorded that there are still around 52,687 poor families still receiving assistance from the Family Hope Program, and an increase in the Poverty Severity Index in 2018-2019 (Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2021 concerning the Banyuwangi Regency National Medium-Term Development Plan, 2021).

The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) is a website-based system used by teams of poverty hunters and village government officials to collect data on the poor in the village. Through this system, the village government is involved in re-collecting data on the poor in their village so that it can be seen the number of poor families in this village and what program interventions the government should provide to address these poor families. Before the smart village program, poverty data at the Social Service and population data at the Population and Civil Registry Offices were separate or not yet combined into one proper database of poor families. As a result, it is difficult for the government to handle poor families in the village through an integrated system in the smart village program where the two previously separate data are combined into one database that contains clear information. Village government officials assist in re-recording and matching poverty data and population data so that data on the poor in the village can be identified based on their name, National Identity Number, address, and house position (geocoding of house coordinates with GPS) and the type of poverty. With clear poverty data, it can make it easier for the government to intervene in poverty management programs that follow the conditions of these poor families.

Figure 2. Sub-district Mapping Display by Number of Poor Population

Figure 3. Per poor population view by region tagging and aid

Poverty handling programs that previously run separately in each Regional Work Unit, through the Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) system, all programs can be integrated into one system. Handling education for poor families can be served through the Banyuwangi Smart Scholarship Assistance Program for students, *the Garda Ampuh Program*, and *siswaasuhsebaya (SAS)* for students. For the health program for poor families, the handling is through a program to receive aid payments and a poor statement letter. The provision of food assistance for poor families can be served through rantangkasih program and the non-cash food program. Business assistance for poor families can be served through the kangoriko program and established partners. There is also a program to renovate residential service houses and build healthy latrines for poor families.

Through sharing poverty management programs that are integrated with a system, it can have a positive impact on handling poor families in Banyuwangi where every year, the poverty rate in Banyuwangi drops drastically.

"Yes, we can report too. So The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) will continue to be developed again. If MSMEs haven't advanced to this class yet, that's why I want to make this one database, the same as the one in the UGDK earlier.

Banyuwangi. This is our innovation savings in 2021. So in 2021, God willing, we will have a lot of savings. This is a lot of programs." (Ms. Lusi, Regional Development Planning, Research and Development Agency, September 2021)

The informant said that Banyuwangi Bappeda created the UGDK (Poverty Emergency Unit) program, which aims to serve the problem of poverty quickly and responsively. This innovation can be created from the cooperation carried out by Bappeda, Health Office, and IT to be later developed by Kominfo. The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) is a website-based system used by teams of poverty hunters and village government officials to collect data on the poor in the village.

Through this system, the village government is involved in re-collecting data on the poor in their village so that it can be seen the number of poor families in this village and what program interventions the government should provide to address these poor families. One of the functions of The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) is to validate the poverty status of the community. In determining poverty validation, The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) uses a village poverty hunter task force under the direction of the Village Head and also a decree for the allocation of funds to fulfill local government programs. In collaboration with smart villages and the Poverty Reduction Coordination Team, the reporting of The Poverty Emergency Unit (UGDK) is centered at the 112 call center. There are also many online complaints and SPMs, which are then handled, while matters related to funding will be followed up through the Device Work Unit. Area. The innovations made by the Banyuwangi Regency government based on the implementation of e-government are expected to increase productivity, including increasing individual effectiveness by reducing administrative overload and providing support for the community. E-government is intended to help change public administration so that it can innovate internally and externally through electronic assistance (Lips, 2020).

UGDK integrates various data such as data from the health office, education office, social service, community and village empowerment agencies, and community welfare as the secretariat of the UGDK. In Banyuwangi itself, the poverty rate has decreased from year to year. Even so, the performance of this ER will continue to be improved. The UGDK is connected to each sub-district in the technical implementation unit for handling poverty. This UGDK implementation unit is located at the local level by continuously provides information on each case's development or handling. Furthermore, Banyuwangi regent Abdullah Azwar Anas said, "The problem of poverty remains our concern. We are currently formulating a formula for responding to poverty quickly. So far, the budget for poverty alleviation has been in place, but sometimes administrative problems hinder the poor from getting services. This requires a "toll road" to integrate with various existing agencies," the regent said when interviewed by detik.com on April 12, 2016. The concept of digital services implemented by the Banyuwangi Regency government, namely G-to-C (Government to Citizens), was built with the aim of so that the government can establish good relations with the community through various access canals so that services for daily needs can be met (Lips, 2020).

Task implementation units located in each sub-district become a responsive team in dealing with various problems experienced by residents in the poor category. Especially the ease of getting access to basic services such as health or education is handled by the task implementation unit, which will be connected online. However, social problems such as poverty, unemployment, or children dropping out of school have received direct attention from the Central Government, which relies on the Ministry of Social Affairs. However, local governments also have a responsibility to address these issues. Local governments have the authority to make policies to help solve poverty problems while still paying attention to other interests. The informant said that the assistance for social assistance was carried out by each assistant who came from the center, the governor, the Ministry of Social Affairs, and the caring ASN. The social assistance in question is the provision of funds or necessities that are selectively selected by the government, especially for people affected by the coronavirus..

This UGDK program is alongside the government's social assistance for necessities, which are responded to through the ASN caring and handled by the Social Service. Caring ASN is an aid program that comes from ASN voluntary donations to help people affected by the Covid 19 pandemic. Caring ASN usually sets targets for assistance from various parties such as the Ministry of Social Affairs, the Provincial Government, and separate reports currently closed.

The informant also stated that this complaint center contains all community data, including E-KTP. So there are two public service products offered by call center 112: Bayuwangi 24 hours and UGDK. Suppose Bayuwangi 24 hours is intended for urgent problems with immediate handling. UGDK focuses more on poverty cases.

Various solutions and public services in Banyuwangi Regency are increasingly innovative and creative. Suppose you were discussing tourist attraction services that have become increasingly sophisticated with applications. So this time, Banyuwangi also presents a 24-hour Banyuwangi breakthrough that handles complaints by solving problems within 24 hours. Banyuwangi 24 hours is the same as the previous complaint center, which was at the 112 call center. Only the cases are not too complicated, so they can be handled no later than 24 hours.

"He can report too. So this UGDK will continue to be developed again. If MSMEs haven't advanced to this class yet, that's why I want to make this one database, the same as the one in the UGDK earlier," (Ms. Lusi, Regional Development Planning, Research and Development Agency, September 2021).

Digitization in Banyuwangi Regency reaps pros and cons, especially from the unpreparedness of the village or sub-district government. However, it differs from Ketapang village, which is quite cooperative in implementing digital innovation within the government. Ketapang Village is known to fully support and contribute to implementing the program in the field.

"yes, but he, he creates his own, creative thing. He creates his own, he commits to update his own data. He wants to know about the widows in this village, tek, you can click it," (Head of Organizational Section 2021).

The regional government at the village level has a large enough contribution to campaign for this digital innovation during a lay society. Innovation aspired to be easy for some to follow but difficult for others. For this reason, socialization and training for the community are important things, and this is where the role of the village government is to continue to socialize various regional innovations carried out to the community so that the goals that have been set can be achieved. The informant said that the use of technology would have a good impact on the performance of the village government so that performance would be faster and more efficient.

Digital innovations that the Banyuwangi local government has carried out will indirectly affect the social pattern of the community. The public will find it easier to accept digitalization nationally because they use regional digital innovations. This digital innovation will help the community easily adapt to increasingly sophisticated technological developments. The informant said that digital innovation, especially in the economy, would increase the circulation of existing money and directly increase people's purchasing power. This increased people's purchasing power, eventually increasing local tax revenues.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, several conclusions and recommendations were set. First, the local government issues a public service policy by developing a digital ecosystem called Smart Kampung. Smart Kampung is an integrated village development program that combines fiber optic-based ICT, productive economic activities, creative economic activities, health-education improvement, and poverty alleviation efforts. Second, in increasing capacity in the regions, to increase the capability of human resources (HR) within the Banyuwangi Regency Government, empowering communities through villages by creating institutional and budgeting institutions in villages, and thirdly, the government supports this program, leadership factors and the provision of regulations are key. In the implementation of the program and the involvement of the community and various parties in social development. Social development is carried out by improving the community's economy. This activity is carried out to optimize the potential and various business networks, with BUMDes as the leading sector.

Meanwhile, this study recommends that the Ministry of Home Affairs and the National Research and Innovation Agency issue Regulations on the Policy for Development of Dynamic Local Government Models. Which is it can have the following aspects. The first is the efforts of Local Economic Growth and Resilience Based on Agriculture, Fisheries, MSMEs, and Tourism Focus on Family Empowerment to Open Job Opportunities and Reduce Poverty; secondly, Accelerating the Development of Economic and Social Infrastructure that is More Equitable by Paying Attention to the Carrying Capacity of the Environment; and the third is to encourage Agile and Dynamic Governance through Digital Transformation to Realize a Productive Bureaucracy and Ease of Doing Business.

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